

An M/M/1 Queueing System with Balking and Impatient Customers under Differentiated Working Vacations

M. Seenivasan^{1@}, N. Siva Sankari^{2§}

¹*Department of Mathematics-CDOE, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, India;*

²*Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, India.*

E-mail Id: @emseeni@yahoo.com, §sivasankarin26@gmail.com,

Abstract:

This paper examines an investigation an M/M/1 Queueing System with Balking and Impatient Customers under Differentiated Working Vacations. The Poisson Process is used to determine the arrival, and the services are distributed exponentially. FCFS was used to serve the customer. There are two different kinds of vacations: the first kind begins after a busy duration, and the second kind starts when there are no customers waiting for the server to get back from vacation. The two vacations are exponentially distributed and independent. During the first kind and the second kind of vacations, services are exponentially distributed. Additionally, the impatience of the waiting consumer during the vacation period is taken into consideration. Balking customer is one who decides not to enter the queue after observing its length. Considering the Stochastic Processes $\{(S(t), N(t)): t \geq 0\}$. This was solved using the matrix geometric method. Some parameters are used in the calculation of performance metrics. Additionally, certain graphical and numerical tables are produced.

Subjects: Arrival rate, Service rate, first kind and second kind – Two types working vacation, Impatience Customers, Balking, Matrix Geometric Method.

AMS Subject classification: 90B22, 60K25 and 60K30.

Introduction:

Queueing System is used in many aspects of daily life, such as computer networks, banking and logistics operations, telecommunications systems, traffic flow systems, and airport scheduling systems. In addition to these, the manufacturing sector also uses queueing systems. Different types of vacation queueing systems exist. When there are no customers in the queue, the server randomly takes a long vacation. The server returns to the queue after an interval, and the server will serve the following customer in line. the server when they return from vacation and discover that the queue is empty, they can begin a new vacation using the multiple vacation strategy. The server will start serving customers who line up in accordance with the current service policy if there is at least one customer waiting. The queueing concept's most obvious characteristic is impatience. Waiting customers are always frustrated and unsatisfied. When customers lose patience, they may decide to leave or skip the queue. This causes a loss of customers.

When a customer refuses, they choose not to join the queue when they arrive because they believe it will be too long, or therefore the wait time will be too long. Doshi [1] investigated vacation-planning queueing systems, and analysis of customer's impatience in queues with server vacations explored Altman and Yechiali [2]. Single-server queues with impatient customers were studied by Baccelli et al. [3], Queueing with impatient customers and ordered service was examined by Barrer [4]. The M/M/1 queue with working vacations and vacation interruptions was examined by Li and Tian [5]. Ibe and Isijola [6] investigated "M/M/1 Multiple Vacation Queueing Systems with Differentiated Vacations", Liu and colleagues [7] examined stochastic decompositions.

M. Seenivasan and R. Abinaya [8] studied "Markovian Queueing Model with Single working Vacation and feedback". Vijayashree and Ambika [9] looked at an M/M/1 queueing model subject to differentiated working vacation and customer impatience. M. Seenivasan, S. Chandiraleka and Mahadevan G [10] explored "Multi Server Queueing model with Multiple Working Vacation using

Matrix Geometric Method”. Seenivasan et al. [11] Studied the “Markovian Queuing Model with Customer’s Impatience in Differentiated Vacations and Feedback Customers”. M. Seenivasan and S. Chandiraleka [12] explored, “Single Server Queuing Model with Multiple Working Vacation and with Server Breakdown”. M. Seenivasan and F. Patricia [13] investigated “A finite Markovian Single Server Queuing Model with Multiple Working Vacation, Catastrophe and Restoration”. Seenivasan et al. [14] examined the “Markovian Queuing Model with Multiple Working Vacation and Catastrophe, Neuro Quantology”, “Queuing System with Single Working Vacation using Matrix Geometric Approach” was studied by Seenivasan et al. [15].

The paper has been divided into the following sections. The structure of the model is illustrated in the second section. In the third section, various numerical examples are provided. The fourth section includes performance analysis with specific values for a certain parameter. The model concludes briefly in the final section.

Model Description:

Consider a M/M/1 Queuing System with Balking and Impatient Customers under Differentiated Working Vacations. FCFS was used to serve the customer. While arrivals follow Poisson processes at a rate of λ , services have an exponential distribution at a rate of μ . Two different kinds of vacations are available. After a busy period, the server takes a first kind of vacation (longer durations), and if no customers return, it takes a second kind of vacation (shorter durations), When at least one customer arrives, the server resumes regular services. The lengths of both vacations are thought to be exponentially distributed and rate-dependent δ_1 and δ_2 respectively. The server services rate is slow when the customer is on vacation μ_1 and μ_2 for both vacation types respectively. A customer impatience timer activates whenever a customer enters and discovers that the servers are on vacation, which is exponentially distributed with rate ω for both vacation types. If the server arrives before their timer runs out, the customer receives service. If not, the customer may quit the line. Due to the length of the wait, the arriving customer does not join it, and the consumers who balk join it at a rate of $\beta' = (1 - \beta)$. The state transition diagram for the model is shown in Fig i.

Fig i. State transition diagram.

We consider $\{(S(t), N(t)):t \geq 0\}$ to be a stochastic process, where $N(t)$ represents the number of customers in the system.

$$S(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{while the server is busy} \\ 1, & \text{while the server is on a First kind vacation.} \\ 2, & \text{while the server is on a Second kind vacation} \end{cases}$$

The following describes the Quasi-Birth and Death (QBD) process and state space:

$$\Omega = \{(1,0) \cup (2,0) \cup (i,j); i = 0,1,2, j \geq 1\}.$$

A technique that utilizes QBD and an infinitesimal generating matrix Q is

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} H & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ J & K & L & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & M & K & L & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & M & K & L & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & M & K & L & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots \end{pmatrix}$$

Where,

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} -(\lambda\beta' + \delta_1) & \delta_1 \\ 0 & -\lambda\beta' \end{pmatrix}; I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \lambda\beta' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda\beta' \end{pmatrix}; J = \begin{pmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ \mu_1 + \omega & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_2 + \omega \end{pmatrix};$$

$$K = \begin{pmatrix} -(\lambda\beta' + \mu) & 0 & 0 \\ \delta_1 & -(\lambda\beta' + \delta_1 + \mu_1 + \omega) & 0 \\ \delta_2 & 0 & -(\lambda\beta' + \delta_2 + \mu_2 + \omega) \end{pmatrix};$$

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda\beta' & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda\beta' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda\beta' \end{pmatrix}; M = \begin{pmatrix} \mu & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_1 + \omega & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_2 + \omega \end{pmatrix}$$

The static probability row matrix is $\xi Q = 0$ (1)

Where $\xi = (\xi_0, \xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \dots \dots \dots)$

From (1),

$$(\xi_0 \xi_1 \xi_2 \xi_3 \dots \dots \dots) \begin{pmatrix} H & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ J & K & L & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & M & K & L & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & M & K & L & 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & M & K & L & 0 & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

$$\xi_0 H + \xi_1 J = 0 \dots\dots(2)$$

$$\xi_0 I + \xi_1 K + \xi_2 M = 0 \dots\dots(3)$$

$$\xi_1 L + \xi_2 K + \xi_3 M = 0 \dots\dots(4)$$

$$\xi_2 L + \xi_3 K + \xi_4 M = 0 \dots\dots(5)$$

⋮

⋮

$$\xi_i L + \xi_{i+1} K + \xi_{i+2} M = 0 \dots\dots(6)$$

We obtain the Geometric Relation

$$\xi_i = \xi_1 R^{i-1}; i \geq 2 \dots\dots(7)$$

Using eqn (3), we obtain

$$R_{n+1} = -K^{-1}(L + R_n^2 M) \dots\dots(8)$$

The normalizing condition is

$$\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1 \dots\dots(9)$$

The column vector e contains all elements that are equal to one.

According to Neuts (1981), the stability condition of a QBD of this type is provided by

$$\xi L e < \xi M e \dots\dots(10)$$

ξ partitioned (ξ_0, ξ_1, ξ_2) the two-generator matrix state probability vector is derived from

$$S = L + K + M,$$

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \delta_1 & -\delta_1 & 0 \\ \delta_2 & 0 & -\delta_2 \end{pmatrix} \dots\dots(11)$$

Additionally, ξ could be shown as stationary so that $\xi M = 0$ and $\xi e = 1$.

As a result, the stability condition for this type of QBD is

$$(\xi_0 + \xi_1 + \xi_2) \lambda \beta' < \xi_0 \mu + \xi_1 \mu_1 + \xi_2 \mu_2 + (\xi_1 + \xi_2) \omega \dots\dots(12)$$

Performance Measures:

The Performance metrics were obtained for varying arrival and service rates are as follows:

$$Pr \{System \text{ is idle}\} = \xi_0 \dots\dots(13)$$

$$\xi(B) = Pr \{Server \text{ is busy}\} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \xi_{0k} \dots\dots(14)$$

$$\xi(1WV) = Pr \{Server \text{ is on First kind working vacation}\} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \xi_{1k} \dots\dots(15)$$

$$\xi(2WV) = Pr \{Server \text{ is on Second kind working vacation}\} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \xi_{2k} \dots\dots(16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(N) &= Pr \{Mean \text{ number of customer present in the system}\} \\ &= \psi(B) + \psi(1WV) + \psi(2WV) \dots\dots(17) \end{aligned}$$

Numerical Analysis:

The Numerical results are obtained when the parameter λ is varied from 1.3 to 1.38, the values of the other parameters remain fixed.

Example (i): $\lambda = 1.3, \mu = 1.9, \mu_1 = 1.7, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.47894 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.18628 & 0.24839 & 0 \\ 0.17049 & 0 & 0.29089 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 1: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		12304E - 5	41398E - 5	53702E - 5
ξ_1	09478E - 5	03056E - 5	12068E - 5	24602E - 5
ξ_2	07166E - 5	00759E - 5	03510E - 5	11435E - 5
ξ_3	04172E - 5	00189E - 5	01021E - 5	05382E - 5
ξ_4	02207E - 5	00047E - 5	00297E - 5	02551E - 5
ξ_5	01116E - 5	00012E - 5	00086E - 5	01214E - 5
ξ_6	00552E - 5	00003E - 5	00025E - 5	00580E - 5
ξ_7	00269E - 5	00001E - 5	00007E - 5	00277E - 5
ξ_8	00130E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5	00132E - 5
ξ_9	00063E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00064E - 5
ξ_{10}	00032E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00032E - 5
ξ_{11}	00014E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00014E - 5
ξ_{12}	00007E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00007E - 5
ξ_{13}	00003E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00003E - 5
ξ_{14}	00002E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5
ξ_{15}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{16}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99998

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.12304, 0.41398)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09478, 0.03056, 0.12068)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}, i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 1. In total, the probability is $0.99998 \cong 1$.

Example (ii): $\lambda = 1.34, \mu = 1.9, \mu_1 = 1.7, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.49368 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.19289 & 0.25512 & 0 \\ 0.17689 & 0 & 0.29866 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 2: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		$12319E - 5$	$39939E - 5$	$52258E - 5$
ξ_1	$09575E - 5$	$03143E - 5$	$11956E - 5$	$24674E - 5$
ξ_2	$07448E - 5$	$00802E - 5$	$03571E - 5$	$11821E - 5$
ξ_3	$04463E - 5$	$00205E - 5$	$01066E - 5$	$05734E - 5$
ξ_4	$02432E - 5$	$00052E - 5$	$00318E - 5$	$02802E - 5$
ξ_5	$01267E - 5$	$00013E - 5$	$00095E - 5$	$01375E - 5$
ξ_6	$00645E - 5$	$00003E - 5$	$00028E - 5$	$00676E - 5$
ξ_7	$00324E - 5$	$00001E - 5$	$00008E - 5$	$00333E - 5$
ξ_8	$00162E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00003E - 5$	$00165E - 5$
ξ_9	$00080E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00001E - 5$	$00081E - 5$
ξ_{10}	$00039E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00039E - 5$
ξ_{11}	$00019E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00019E - 5$
ξ_{12}	$00009E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00009E - 5$
ξ_{13}	$00005E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00005E - 5$
ξ_{14}	$00002E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00002E - 5$
ξ_{15}	$00001E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00001E - 5$
ξ_{16}	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$
Total				0.99994

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.12319, 0.39939)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09575, 0.03143, 0.11956)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}, i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 2. In total, the probability is $0.99994 \cong 1$.

Example (iii): $\lambda = 1.36, \mu = 1.9, \mu_1 = 1.7, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.50105 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.19621 & 0.25845 & 0 \\ 0.18013 & 0 & 0.30252 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 3: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		$12091E - 5$	$39231E - 5$	$51322E - 5$
ξ_1	$09651E - 5$	$03125E - 5$	$12024E - 5$	$24800E - 5$
ξ_2	$07615E - 5$	$00808E - 5$	$03637E - 5$	$12060E - 5$
ξ_3	$04629E - 5$	$00209E - 5$	$01100E - 5$	$05938E - 5$
ξ_4	$02559E - 5$	$00054E - 5$	$00333E - 5$	$02946E - 5$
ξ_5	$01353E - 5$	$00014E - 5$	$00101E - 5$	$01468E - 5$
ξ_6	$00698E - 5$	$00004E - 5$	$00030E - 5$	$00732E - 5$

ξ_7	00356E - 5	00001E - 5	00009E - 5	00366E - 5
ξ_8	00180E - 5	00000E - 5	00003E - 5	00183E - 5
ξ_9	00091E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00092E - 5
ξ_{10}	00046E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00046E - 5
ξ_{11}	00023E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00023E - 5
ξ_{12}	00012E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00012E - 5
ξ_{13}	00006E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00006E - 5
ξ_{14}	00003E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00003E - 5
ξ_{15}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{16}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99998

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.12091, 0.39231)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09651, 0.03125, 0.12024)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 3. In total, the probability is $0.99998 \cong 1$.

Example (iv): $\lambda = 1.38, \mu = 1.9, \mu_1 = 1.7, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.50843 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.19955 & 0.26178 & 0 \\ 0.18338 & 0 & 0.30634 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 4: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		12313E - 5	38501E - 5	50814E - 5
ξ_1	09656E - 5	03223E - 5	11824E - 5	24703E - 5
ξ_2	07721E - 5	00844E - 5	03622E - 5	12187E - 5
ξ_3	04758E - 5	00221E - 5	01109E - 5	06088E - 5
ξ_4	02667E - 5	00058E - 5	00339E - 5	03064E - 5
ξ_5	01429E - 5	00015E - 5	00104E - 5	01548E - 5
ξ_6	00749E - 5	00004E - 5	00032E - 5	00785E - 5
ξ_7	00387E - 5	00001E - 5	00010E - 5	00398E - 5
ξ_8	00199E - 5	00000E - 5	00003E - 5	00202E - 5
ξ_9	00102E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00103E - 5
ξ_{10}	00052E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00052E - 5
ξ_{11}	00026E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00026E - 5
ξ_{12}	00013E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00013E - 5
ξ_{13}	00007E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00007E - 5
ξ_{14}	00003E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00003E - 5
ξ_{15}	00002E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5
ξ_{16}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{17}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99996

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.12313, 0.38501)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09656, 0.03223, 0.11824)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which

have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 4. In total, the probability is $0.99996 \cong 1$.

The parameter μ is varied from 1.8 to 1.86 and numerical results are obtained by fixing the values of the other parameters.

Example (v): $\lambda = 1.2, \mu = 1.8, \mu_1 = 1.6, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.46667 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.18512 & 0.23716 & 0 \\ 0.16149 & 0 & 0.27118 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 5: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		11845E - 5	44008E - 5	55853E - 5
ξ_1	09489E - 5	02809E - 5	11969E - 5	24267E - 5
ξ_2	06881E - 5	00666E - 5	03246E - 5	10793E - 5
ξ_3	03859E - 5	00158E - 5	00880E - 5	04897E - 5
ξ_4	01972E - 5	00037E - 5	00239E - 5	02248E - 5
ξ_5	00966E - 5	00009E - 5	00065E - 5	01040E - 5
ξ_6	00463E - 5	00002E - 5	00018E - 5	00483E - 5
ξ_7	00219E - 5	00000E - 5	00005E - 5	00224E - 5
ξ_8	00103E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00104E - 5
ξ_9	00048E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00048E - 5
ξ_{10}	00023E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00023E - 5
ξ_{11}	00011E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00011E - 5
ξ_{12}	00005E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00005E - 5
ξ_{13}	00002E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5
ξ_{14}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{15}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99999

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.11845, 0.44008)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09489, 0.02809, 0.11969)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 5. In total, the probability is $0.99999 \cong 1$.

Example (vi): $\lambda = 1.2, \mu = 1.82, \mu_1 = 1.6, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.46154 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.18339 & 0.23716 & 0 \\ 0.16008 & 0 & 0.27118 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 6: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		11906E - 5	44214E - 5	56120E - 5

ξ_1	09433E - 5	02824E - 5	12022E - 5	24279E - 5
ξ_2	06796E - 5	00669E - 5	03260E - 5	10725E - 5
ξ_3	03781E - 5	00159E - 5	00884E - 5	04824E - 5
ξ_4	01916E - 5	00038E - 5	00239E - 5	02193E - 5
ξ_5	00929E - 5	00009E - 5	00065E - 5	01003E - 5
ξ_6	00441E - 5	00002E - 5	00018E - 5	00461E - 5
ξ_7	00207E - 5	00001E - 5	00005E - 5	00213E - 5
ξ_8	00096E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00097E - 5
ξ_9	00045E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00045E - 5
ξ_{10}	00021E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00021E - 5
ξ_{11}	00009E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00009E - 5
ξ_{12}	00004E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00004E - 5
ξ_{13}	00002E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5
ξ_{14}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{15}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99997

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.11906, 0.44214)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09433, 0.02824, 0.12022)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 6. In total, the probability is $0.99997 \cong 1$.

Example (vii): $\lambda = 1.2, \mu = 1.84, \mu_1 = 1.6, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.45651 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.18169 & 0.23716 & 0 \\ 0.15872 & 0 & 0.27118 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 7: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		11966E - 5	44414E - 5	56380E - 5
ξ_1	09377E - 5	02838E - 5	12073E - 5	24288E - 5
ξ_2	06713E - 5	00673E - 5	03274E - 5	10660E - 5
ξ_3	03706E - 5	00159E - 5	00888E - 5	04753E - 5
ξ_4	01862E - 5	00038E - 5	00241E - 5	02141E - 5
ξ_5	00895E - 5	00009E - 5	00065E - 5	00969E - 5
ξ_6	00421E - 5	00002E - 5	00018E - 5	00441E - 5
ξ_7	00195E - 5	00001E - 5	00005E - 5	00201E - 5
ξ_8	00089E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5	00090E - 5
ξ_9	00041E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00041E - 5
ξ_{10}	00019E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00019E - 5
ξ_{11}	00009E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00009E - 5
ξ_{12}	00004E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00004E - 5
ξ_{13}	00002E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00002E - 5
ξ_{14}	00001E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00001E - 5
ξ_{15}	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5	00000E - 5
Total				0.99999

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.11966, 0.44414)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09377, 0.02838, 0.12073)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 7. In total, the probability is $0.99999 \cong 1$.

Example (viii): $\lambda = 1.2, \mu = 1.86, \mu_1 = 1.6, \mu_2 = 1.5, \delta_1 = 1.1, \delta_2 = 0.8, \omega = 0.5, \beta' = 0.7$ and

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.45161 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.18006 & 0.23716 & 0 \\ 0.15738 & 0 & 0.27118 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 8: Probability Vectors

ξ_i	ξ_{0i}	ξ_{1i}	ξ_{2i}	Total
ξ_0		$12024E - 5$	$44606E - 5$	$56630E - 5$
ξ_1	$09321E - 5$	$02852E - 5$	$12122E - 5$	$24295E - 5$
ξ_2	$06631E - 5$	$00676E - 5$	$03287E - 5$	$10594E - 5$
ξ_3	$03634E - 5$	$00160E - 5$	$00891E - 5$	$04685E - 5$
ξ_4	$01810E - 5$	$00038E - 5$	$00242E - 5$	$02090E - 5$
ξ_5	$00862E - 5$	$00009E - 5$	$00066E - 5$	$00937E - 5$
ξ_6	$00401E - 5$	$00002E - 5$	$00018E - 5$	$00421E - 5$
ξ_7	$00184E - 5$	$00001E - 5$	$00005E - 5$	$00190E - 5$
ξ_8	$00084E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00001E - 5$	$00085E - 5$
ξ_9	$00038E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00038E - 5$
ξ_{10}	$00017E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00017E - 5$
ξ_{11}	$00008E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00008E - 5$
ξ_{12}	$00004E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00004E - 5$
ξ_{13}	$00002E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00002E - 5$
ξ_{14}	$00001E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00001E - 5$
ξ_{15}	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$	$00000E - 5$
Total				0.99997

From the R matrix in Equations (1) and (7), the probability vectors ξ_0 and ξ_1 have been generated. In the normalizing condition $\xi_0 e + \xi_1 (I - R)^{-1} e = 1$, these values are substituted to obtain $\xi_0 = (0.12024, 0.44606)$ and $\xi_1 = (0.09321, 0.02852, 0.12122)$. The remaining vectors ξ_i 's, which have been generated using the relationship $\xi_i = \xi_0 R^{i-1}$, $i \geq 2$, are all shown in table 8. In total, the probability is $0.99997 \cong 1$.

Table 9: Performance Measures for Arrival rate (λ)

λ	$\xi(B)$	$\xi(1WV)$	$\xi(2WV)$	$\xi(N)$
1.3	0.58176	0.05414	0.23993	0.87583
1.34	0.62892	0.05660	0.24300	0.92852
1.36	0.65000	0.05700	0.24411	0.96096
1.38	0.68039	0.05715	0.24566	0.98517

Fig ii-(a)

Fig ii-(b)

Fig ii-(c)

Fig ii-(d)

Fig ii: (a)-(d). Performance Measures for Arrival rate (λ)

Fig ii: (a)–(d) illustrates that as the arrival rate (λ) increases, the probability of the system being idle $\xi(E)$ decreases. Conversely, the probabilities of the server being busy $\xi(B)$, the server having n customers overall $\xi(N)$, being in a Second Kind Working Vacation $\xi(2WV)$, and in a First Kind Working Vacation $\xi(1WV)$ all increase.

Table 10: Performance Measures for Service rate (μ)

μ	$\xi(B)$	$\xi(1WV)$	$\xi(2WV)$	$\xi(N)$
1.8	0.53564	0.04820	0.22533	0.80917
1.82	0.52342	0.04855	0.22626	0.79823
1.84	0.51193	0.04877	0.22725	0.78795
1.86	0.50089	0.04900	0.22818	0.77807

Fig iii-(a)

Fig iii-(b)

Fig iii-(c)

Fig iii-(d)

Fig iii: (a)-(d). Performance Measures for Service rate (μ)

Fig iii: (a)–(d) illustrates that as the service rate (μ) increases, the probability that the system is idle ($\xi(E)$) increases, Correspondingly, the probability that the server is busy ($\xi(B)$) decreases, A slight increase is observed in the probability of the server being on a First Kind Working Vacation ($\xi(1WV)$) the probability of being on a Second Kind Working Vacation ($\xi(2WV)$) also increase. the probability that there are n customers in the system ($\xi(N)$) decreases

Conclusion:

We have looked at the M/M/1 Queueing System with Balking and Impatient Customers under Differentiated Working Vacations. The topic of customer impatience and balking has been covered here. When a customer's service is not finished before their timer goes off, they exit the line and never come back. Balking occurs when an appliance decides not to join the queue upon arrival, possibly due to the length of the queue. To solve the model, matrix geometric methods were applied. Probability vectors are generated by applying varying values to the arrival rate and service rate. Furthermore, several performance measurements were constructed and also Graphical representation.

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